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OBSTETRICS AND GYNECOLOGY

1. **An V. Andrey, Sharipova Kh. Feruza**
THE CLINICAL COURSE OF FOCAL MYOCARDITIS IN PREGNANT.....10
2. **Kamalova I. Malika, Askarova K. Fatima**
UTERINE MUCOSAL MORPHOLOGY OF INTRAUTERINE CONTRACEPTIVE USE
(LITERATURE REVIEW).....15
3. **Nasimova R. Nigina**
THE ROLE OF ESTROGENIC DEFICIENCY IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND
PROGRESSION OF GENITAL PROLAPSE.....20

HEMATOLOGY

4. **Kayumov A. Abdurakhman, Ibragimova M. Gulchehra, Achilova U. Ozoda**
IMMUNE THROMBOCYTOPENIA A MODERN VIEW OF DIAGNOSIS AND
TREATMENT: LITERATURE REVIEW.....26

PEDIATRIC SURGERY

5. **Kamolov J. Sardor, Mavlyanov Sh. Farxod, Yangiyev A. Baxtiyor**
BIOIMPEDANCE PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS WITH EMERGENCY ABDOMINAL
PATHOLOGY.....35
6. **Tuxtayev M. Firdavs, Mavlyanov Sh. Farxod, Mavlyanov X. Shavkat**
RESULTS OF BIOIMPEDANCE ANALYSIS IN CHILDREN WITH EMERGENCY
PATHOLOGY OF THE URINARY SYSTEM.....41
7. **Mavlyanov Sh. Farhod, Ulmasov G. Firdaus, Allazov N. Feruz, Mavlyanov Kh. Shavkat,
Tursunov E. Sanjar.**
SURGICAL TREATMENT OF A TUMOR OF THE ABDOMINAL CAVITY ISSUING
FROM THE WALL OF THE STOMACH IN A CHILD: A CLINICAL CASE.....46

RADIOLOGY

8. **Xalikulov Sh. Elbek, Sharopov Sh. Sadullo.**
NEUROSONOGRAPHY AS A METHOD OF INTRAOPERATIVE NAVIGATION IN THE
TREATMENT OF MULTILEVEL HYDROCEPHALIA.....52
9. **Usarov Sh. Mukhriddin**
OPTIMIZATION AND IMPORTANCE OF ULTRASOUND DIAGNOSTIC METHODS IN
THE CHOICE OF TACTICS FOR THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS WITH CERVICAL
OSTEOCHONDROSIS.....56

OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY

10. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Xayitov A. Alisher, Dustboboyev S. Dilshod**
MODERN ASPECTS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXUDATIVE OTITIS MEDIA.....62
11. **Nasretdinova T. Makhzuna, Normirova N. Nargiza, Shadiev E. Anvar**
AUDITORY ADAPTATION IN PATIENTS WITH PERIPHERAL AND CENTRAL
HEARING IMPAIRMENT.....70

MORPHOLOGY

12. **Urinov M. Alisher, Otajonov O. Ilhom, Akhmedova B. Dilafruz**
STUDY OF CHANGES IN SOME BIOCHEMICAL INDICATORS OF BLOOD IN
SIMULATION OF EXPERIMENTAL LIVER DAMAGE.....76

13. **Nuraliev A. Nekqadam, Murotov F. Nurshod.**
THE RESULTS OF DETERMINING THE DEGREE OF INFLUENCE OF THE GENETICALLY MODIFIED SHADE ON THE REGULATORY MICROFLORA OF THE COLON OF LABORATORY ANIMALS.....81
14. **Khamidova M. Farida, Zhovlieva B. Mavlyuda**
MORPHOLOGICAL AND FUNCTIONAL FEATURES OF THE STRUCTURE OF THE BRONCHI IN EXPERIMENTAL CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASES.....91
15. **Sabirova Sh. Dilnoza, Oripov S. Firdavs**
MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE ADRENAL CORT OF RAT OFFSPRING IN ONTOGENESIS UNDER THE CONDITIONS OF INTRAUTERINE EXPOSURE TO PESTICIDES THROUGH THE MOTHER'S ORGANISM (REVIEW ARTICLE).....100
16. **Boboev I. Askar, Oripov S. Firdavs**
MORPHOLOGY NEAR THE BALL-BLADYING PARENCHYMA OF THE RABBIT LIVER WITH EXPERIMENTAL CALCULOSIS CHOLECYSTITIS.....108
17. **Kurbonov R. Khurshed, Oripov S. Firdavs, Deev V. Roman**
EFFECT OF OCTACALCIUM PHOSPHATE AND ITS COMBINED FORMS ON BONE REGENERATION.....114

NEUROLOGY

18. **Kamalova I. Malika, Khaidarov K. Nodirjon, Teshayev Zh. Shukhrat.**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF SOME RISK FACTORS FOR STROKE IN WOMEN.....122
19. **Sheryigitova I. Nigina, Muzaffarova Sh. Nargiza, Khakimova Z. Sohiba.**
COGNITIVE AND ASTHENIC DISORDERS AFTER COVID-19.....129

ONCOLOGY

20. **Kuliev A. Aziz, Tursunov M. Odil, Ulmasov G. Firdavs, Urazov S. Numon, Toshov T. Alizhon**
FEATURES OF DEVELOPMENT OF MECHANICAL JAUNDICE IN GASTRIC CANCER AND METHODS OF ITS ELIMINATION.....136
21. **Polatova Sh. Jamilya, Tagaev A. Jasur**
GLOBAL STATUS OF THE PROBLEMS OF DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF MELANOMA AMONG PATIENTS WITH MELANOCYTIC LESIONS AND NEOPLASMS.....143
22. **Rakhimov M. Nodir, Abdurakhmonov A. Jurabek, Shakhanova Sh. Shakhnoza, Sulimova G.Olga**
PATOGENESIS OF PERITONEAL ASCITES IN RECURRENT OVARIAN CANCER.....152
23. **Djuraev D. Mirjalol, Shamuradov I. Ilxom**
THE ROLE OF ENDOSCOPIC STENTING IN ESOPHAGEAL CANCER COMPLICATED BY FISTULA.....159
24. **Alimkhodzhayeva T. Lola, Norbekova Kh. Munira, Zievidinova S. Soniya, Mirzayeva A. Matlyuba, Khusanova J. Makhinabonu**
CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF TUMOR-INFILTRATING LYMPHOCYTES IN BREAST CANCER.....166
25. **Alimkhodzhayeva T. Lola, Norbekova Kh. Munira, Zievidinova S. Soniya, Mirzayeva A. Matlyuba, Khusanova J. Makhinabonu**
THE BASIC APPROACHES TO STUDYING THE LYMPHATIC SYSTEM IN BREAST CANCER(LITERATURE REVIEW).....177
26. **Rakhimov M. Nodir, Tulanov T. Begzod, Shakhanova Sh. Shakhnoza, Aslsnova M. Lobar**
PATHOGENETIC ASPECTS OF CANCER ANOREXIA.....192

OPHTHALMOLOGY

27. **Kadirova M. Aziza, Khasanova A. Dildora.**
CASE FROM PRACTICE: CONGENITAL ANOMALY OF OPTIC DISC EXCAVATION. «MORNING GLORY» SYNDROME.....202
28. **Allayarov T. Azimbek, Rizayev A. Jasur, Yusupov A. Amin, Xakimova Sh. Mavluda.**
THE STATE OF OPHTHALMOLOGICAL CARE AND ITS IMPROVEMENT IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC RETINOPATHY (LITERATURE REVIEW).....210

PEDIATRICS

29. **Tairova B. Sakina**
PREVALENCE OF ALLERGIC DISEASES AMONG CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS.....215
30. **Tairova B. Sakina, Mukhamadiyeva A. Lola**
IMMUNOLOGICAL ASPECTS IN YOUNG CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS.....220
31. **Tairova B. Sakina**
CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS: AN IMMUNOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVE (LITERATURE REVIEW).....226
32. **Fayziyeva R. Ugilbibi, Normamato V. Kh. Dilmurod. Mamadiyeva N. Zarifa**
CHARACTERISTICS OF BRONCHOBSTRUCTIVE SYNDROME IN CHILDREN.....231

PSYCHIATRY

33. **Kenjaeva K. Nargiza, Rizaev A. Jasur, Umirov E. Safar, Baymirov L. Sanjar.**
CLINICAL DYNAMICS OF DEPENDENCE TO PSYCHOACTIVE SUBSTANCES AND ITS DETERMINANTS.....237
34. **Baymirov L. Sanjar, Ochilov U. Ulugbek, Turayev T. Bobir**
CLINICAL FEATURES OF THE ABUSE OF VARIOUS DRUGS IN PATIENTS WITH ALCOHOLISM.....247

REHABILITATION AND SPORTS MEDICINE

35. **Mavlyanova F. Zilola, Kim A. Olga, Xudoykulova V. Farida, Raxmatullina R. Luiza, Bulyakova A. Gulnaz, Akhmadeeva Leila.**
POSSIBILITIES OF PERSONALIZED REHABILITATION AFTER A STROKE USING TELETECHNOLOGIES AND PREDICTION OF OUTCOMES BASED ON CLINICAL AND NEURORADIOLOGICAL STUDIES.....252
36. **Kamilova T. Roza, Mavlyanova F. Zilola, Basharova M. Laylo, Isakova I. Lola, Burxanova L. Gulnoza.**
COMPARATIVE ASSESSMENT OF ACTUAL FOOD CONSUMPTION BY CHILDREN OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS WITH DIFFERENT DIETARY INTAKE.....261

STOMATOLOGY AND MAXILLOFACIAL SURGERY

37. **Latipova B. Sitora**
INVESTIGATION OF THE CLINICAL EFFICACY OF ORAL MUCOSA TREATMENT AFTER CHEMOTHERAPY: LITERATURE REVIEW.....270
38. **Abdullaev Sh. Dilmurod**
ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED AND SOME FEATURES OF CYTOKINE PROFILE IN MIXED SALIVA OF PATIENTS WITH GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT DISEASE.....279

39. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Akhmedov A. Alisher**
IMPROVING DENTAL CARE IN UZBEKISTAN USING A CONCEPTUAL APPROACH TO IMPROVE ITS QUALITY.....287
40. **Sharopov G. Sanzhar, Tojiev I. Feruz, Azimov I. Mukhammadjon, Inoyatov Sh. Amrillo, Ismoilkhodjaeva G. Komila**
CLINICAL AND RADIOLOGICAL MANIFESTATIONS OF SECONDARY MAXILLARY DEFORMITIES IN PATIENTS WITH UNI- AND BILATERAL CLEFT LIP AND PALATE AFTER PRIMARY LIP AND PALATE SURGERIES.....294

THERAPY

41. **Ermatov J. Nizom, Nasirdinov Z. Mavlonjon, Ishmetov P. Sherzod, Oltiev Sh. Amrillo, Kasimova E. Kizilgul.**
EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE DAILY DIET OF SCHOOLCHILDREN SUFFERING FROM IRON DEFICIENCY ANEMIA FROM ENRICHED LOCAL PROTEIN-CONTAINING PRODUCTS.....301
42. **Ermatov J. Nizom, Abdulkhakov U. Ikhtiyor, Shukurov N. Anvar, Nasirdinov Z. Mavlon, Kasimova E. Kizilgul**
HYGIENIC FEATURES OF DIABETES PREVENTION.....308
43. **Tashkenbayeva N. Eleonora, Esankulov O. Mukhammad**
SIGNIFICANCE OF UROMODULIN IN THE DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE.....318
44. **Tairov R. Doston, Berdiev H. Doniyor**
STRUCTURAL CHANGES IN THE CARDIOVASCULAR SYSTEM IN PATIENTS WITH GOUT.....331
45. **Rizaev A. Jasur, Qilichev A. Anvar, Olimjonova J. Farangiz**
RISK FACTORS FOR CARDIOVASCULAR DISEASE AFTER CORONARY ARTERY BYPASS GRAFTING IN PATIENTS WITH ISCHEMIC HEART DISEASE.....339
46. **Isirgapova N. Sarvinoz, Sultonov N. Nodir**
IMPACT OF HORMONAL CHANGES ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE IN PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE 5TH STAGE.....349
47. **Yakubov V. Abduljalol, Pulaniva I. Nargiza, Saidova A. Shakhnoza, Musayeva J. Lola**
PROSPECTIVE DIRECTIONS FOR THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC HEART FAILURE.....360
48. **Xaydarova D. Dilrabo, Tashkenbaeva N. Eleonora**
CLINICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE COURSE AND CRITERIA FOR DIAGNOSTICS OF CHRONIC OBSTRUCTIVE PULMONARY DISEASE IN PATIENTS WITH COVID-19 PNEUMONIA.....366

PHARMACOLOGY

49. **Boboyev M. Behzod**
CLINICAL EVALUATION OF THE CHRONIC TOXICITY OF THE NEW DRUG «TIOSIN», CONSISTING WITH A COMPLEX COMBINATION OF THE MICROELEMENT ZINC AND LIPOIC ACID.....376
50. **Allazov A. Salakh. Iskandarov N. Yusuf**
LOCAL HEMOSTATIC IN UROLOGICAL BLEEDING.....383

SURGERY

51. **Shodmonov A. Akbar, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Askarov A. Pulat**
EVALUATION OF THE RESULTS OF THE TREATMENT OF NON-SPECIFIC ULCERATIVE COLITIS WITH THE APPLICATION OF PLASMAPHERESIS.....390
52. **Rizayev A. Jasur, Kurbaniyazov B. Zafar, Saidov B. Zohir, Abduraxmanov Sh. Diyor.**
ANTEGRADE ANGIOSCLEROTHERAPY OF THE LEFT TESTICULAR VEIN.....397

53.	Nazarov N. Zokir SURGICAL TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED FORMS OF CHOLELITHIASIS IN ELDERLY AND SENILE PATIENTS (LITERATURE REVIEW).....	407
54.	Shamratov Z. Shokir, Akhmedov M. Yusuf, Yusupov S. Anvar, Saidov A. Maksud MYOCARDIAL PROTECTION METHODS IN CARDIAC SURGERY PRACTICE (REVIEW ARTICLE).....	417
55.	Ruziboev A. Sanjar, Yunusova F. Guzal, Yunusov T. Oybek EFFICIENCY OF APPLICATION OF DOMESTIC HEMOSTATIC IMPLANT "HEMOBEN" IN SEVERELY BURNED PATIENTS.....	424
56.	Abdullaev A. Sayfulla, Xujabaev T. Safarboy, Dusiyarov M. Muhammad TACTICS OF TREATMENT OF ACUTE COMMERCIAL INTESTINAL OBSTRUCTION.....	431
57.	Sherbekov A. Ulugbek, Xaydarova O. Laylo, Abdurakhmanov Sh. Diyor CLINICAL FEATURES OF HERNIOPLASTY AND ABDOMINOPLASTY WITH COMPLICATED ABDOMINOPTOSIS IN VENTAL HERNIAS.....	440
58.	Sherbekov A. Ulugbek, Xaydarova O. Laylo SURGICAL TREATMENT OF VENTAL HERNIAS IN PATIENTS WITH MORBID OBESITY AND ABDOMINOPTOSIS.....	446
59.	Umedov A. Xushvaqt OUR EXPERIENCE IN CONSERVATIVE TREATMENT OF SPLEEN INJURY IN CLOSED ABDOMINAL TRAUMA.....	451
60.	Umedov A. Xushvaqt POSSIBILITIES OF VIDEOLAPAROSCOPIC DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF ISOLATED AND COMBINED LIVER DAMAGE.....	456
61.	Sattarov S. Inayat, Matmurotov J. Kuvondik, Yakubov Y. Ilyosbek, Rakhimov D. Dadakhon. WAYS TO IMPROVE REVASCULARIZATION RESULTS IN PATIENTS WITH DIABETIC FOOT SYNDROME.....	461

ORIGINAL ARTICLES

62.	Giyasov A. Zaynitdin, Khaydarov R. Khasanali, Siddikov U. Bokijon ANALYSIS OF COMMISSION FORENSIC MEDICAL EXAMINATIONS RELATED TO THE ACTIVITIES OF OBSTETRICIAN-GYNECOLOGISTS.....	468
63.	DAMINOV Feruz Asatullaevich ASPECTS OF SURGICAL TREATMENT OF DEEP BURN IN ELDERLY AND SENILE AGE.....	475
64.	SAMIEV Asliddin Sayitovich, KHAMIDULLAEVA Mohinur Maksatullo qizi COMPLEX REHABILITATION MEASURES IN PATIENTS SUFFERING WITH RADICULOPATHIES OF THE VERTEBROGENOUS LUMBAR AREA.....	481

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PREVALENCE OF ALLERGIC DISEASES AMONG CHILDREN WITH CONGENITAL HEART DEFECTS

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ANNOTATION

Objective: to study the frequency of allergy in children with congenital heart disease (CHD).

Materials and methods: A survey of 103 children (from 1 month to 3 years) was conducted, who were hospitalized in the department of cardiac surgery examination at the regional children's multidisciplinary medical center (RChMMC) in Samarkand in the period from 2021 to 2022.

Results: The prevalence of allergic diseases (AD) in children with CHD was 19.41%. The data obtained by us make it possible to classify sick children with CHD as a risk group for the formation of AD.

Conclusions. Currently, despite the fact that more and more children are born with CHD, their surgical correction gives favorable results. From this point of view, in the treatment of children with CHD, along with surgical treatment, it is also necessary to correct the comorbid pathology, in this case, allergic diseases.

Key words: congenital heart disease, allergic diseases, comorbid conditions, prevalence

ТАИРОВА Сакина Баходировна
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РАСПРОСТРАНЕННОСТЬ АЛЛЕРГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ СРЕДИ ДЕТЕЙ С ВРОЖДЕННЫМИ ПОРОКАМИ СЕРДЦА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Цель: изучить частоту аллергии у детей с врожденными пороками сердца (ВПС).

Материалы и методы: Проведено обследование 103 детей (от 1 месяца до 3 лет), находившихся на стационарном лечении в отделении кардиохирургии Областного детского многопрофильного медицинского центра (ОДММЦ) г. Самарканда в период с 2021 по 2022 годы.

Полученные результаты: Распространенность аллергических заболеваний (АЗ) у детей с ВПС составила 19,41%. Полученные нами данные позволяют отнести больных детей с ВПС к группе риска по формированию АЗ.

Выводы. В настоящее время, несмотря на то, что все больше детей рождается с ВПС, их хирургическая коррекция дает благоприятные результаты. С этой точки зрения при лечении детей с ВПС наряду с хирургическим лечением необходима коррекция коморбидной патологии, в данном случае аллергических заболеваний.

Ключевые слова: врожденные пороки сердца, аллергические заболевания, коморбидные состояния, распространенность

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TUG'MA YURAK NUQSONI BOR BOLALAR ORASIDA ALLERGIK KASALLIKLARNING TARQALISHI

ANNOTATSIYA

Maqsad: tug'ma yurak nuqsonlari (TYuN) bo'lgan bolalarda allergiya chastotasini o'rganish.

Material va metodlar: 2021-2022-yillarda Samarqand shahridagi Viloyat bolalar ko'p tarmoqli tibbiyot markazi (VBKTTM) kardiojarrohlik bo'limiga yotqizilgan 103 nafar (1 oylikdan 3 yoshgacha) bolalar o'rtasida tadqiqot o'tkazildi.

Natijalar: TYuN bilan og'rigan bolalarda allergik kasalliklarning (AK) tarqalishi 19,41% ni tashkil etdi. Bizning ma'lumotlarimiz tug'ma yurak kasalligi bo'lgan kasal bolalarni AK shakllanishi uchun xavf guruhiga tasniflash imkonini beradi.

Xulosa. Ayni paytda, ko'plab bolalar yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari bilan tug'ilishiga qaramay, ularni jarrohlik yo'li bilan tuzatish ijobiy natijalar beradi. Shu nuqtai nazardan qaraganda, TYuN bilan og'rigan bolalarni davolashda jarrohlik davolash bilan bir qatorda, komorbid patologiyani, jumladan allergik kasalliklarni korreksiya qilish zarur.

Kalit so'zlar: tug'ma yurak nuqsoni, allergik kasalliklar, komorbid holatlar, tarqalish

INTRODUCTION. Congenital heart defects are the most common birth defects, and allergic diseases (AD) are common diseases in childhood. AD has attracted more and more attention in recent decades due to its increasing prevalence among the population. Numerous epidemiological studies studying the prevalence of AD in the world objectively reflect the steady growth of allergopathology, especially in children. Their co-occurrence is not well understood, but may increase due to similar risk factors or immune dysregulation associated with inflammation at an early age.

The relevance of this problem is due not only to the high prevalence, but also to the tendency to increase the proportion of more severe, combined CHD with frequent adverse outcomes in the first year of life.

OBJECTIVE: to study was to study the frequency of allergy in children with congenital heart disease (CHD) according to the pediatric cardiosurgical department of the Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center of Samarkand. This study aims to compare the prevalence of allergic diseases in children with CHD and their healthy siblings, as well as to assess their impact on the physical functioning of children with AD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. A survey of 103 children (from 1 month to 3 years) was conducted, who were hospitalized in the Department of Cardiac Surgery and outpatient examination at the Regional Children's Multidisciplinary Medical Center (RChMMC) of Samarkand in the period for 2021 to 2022, which were divided into I and II groups:

- Group I consisted of 72 operated children (main group) with congenital septal heart defects.
- Group II consisted of 31 children (comparison group) who received only conservative treatment, due to the presence of contraindications to surgery.

To achieve this goal, a set of studies was carried out, including clinical and instrumental data, including ultrasound - echocardiography (EchoCG) with Doppler ultrasound to assess the anatomical structure and function of the heart and large vessels using the Vivid apparatus S 60 N according to the standard method. In addition to echocardiography of the heart, all children underwent

electrocardiography (ECG), chest x-ray, and laboratory methods. In addition, additional research methods were carried out in the form of measuring anthropometric parameters.

Parent-reported data on allergic reactions to drugs, foods, and plant pollen were collected.

RESULTS. When studying the prevalence of AD among children with congenital heart diseases in the districts of Samarkand and regions and the Republic of Uzbekistan, in terms of referral and hospitalization in the pediatric cardiosurgical department, a trend was revealed in the following order: in Urgut district 8,73% (n = 9), in Ishtikhan district 6,79% (n =7), in Kushrabad district 2,91% (n =3) and in Jizzakh region 0,97% (n =1).

Within 5 years, the number of patients admitted to the Department of Cardiac Surgery of the Samarkand RChMMC has been progressing (Fig. 1.).

Fig. 1. The number of patients admitted to the Department of Cardiac Surgery of the Samarkand RChMMC for the period 2018-2022.

We noted a significant increase in the number of operated patients with CHD during the period 2018-2022, that is, from year to year, the number of patients increased almost 2 times (Fig. 2.).

Fig. 2. The number of operated patients with CHD for the period 2018-2022.

It should be noted that during the survey period there was a trend towards an increase in CHD in children in all regions.

According to the literature, the ratio of patients depending on gender is different. According to the results of our research, girls numerically predominate over boys. Among the examined children there were 48 boys (46.60%) and 55 girls (53.39%).

Children from the main group and the comparison group had an allergic reaction to drugs such as azithromycin, chikoncil; for food products: berries-raspberries, strawberries, citrus fruits-tangerines, oranges; for sweets: chocolates; on plants; also, some parents found it difficult to answer and did not know what could cause an allergic reaction in children. An allergic reaction to all the above allergens in 70% manifested itself in the form of rashes on the body, 19,44% (n = 14), 19,35% (n = 6) had the same level of allergic diseases.

Of allergic reactions, food allergy 55% (n =11), drug allergy 30% (n =6) and allergic rhinitis 15% (n =3) were intermittently observed. Allergic reactions in children were manifested in the form of rashes on the body, rhinoconjunctivitis, itching, redness and peeling of the skin. In all children with AD, antihistamines were found, with the elimination of causative inflammation.

The prevalence of AD in children with CHD was 19,41%. Our data allow us to classify sick children with congenital heart disease as a risk group for the formation of AD.

Currently, despite the fact that more and more children are born with CHD, their surgical correction gives favorable results. From this point of view, in the treatment of children with CHD, along with surgical treatment, it is also necessary to correct the comorbid pathology, in this case, allergic diseases. This improves the quality of life of children after surgery, and also ensures age-related adaptation to social life.

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